

Study on the removal of PFAS during hydrothermal carbonization of sewage sludge

G. Altiparmaki^a, G. Gatidou^b, Emma Knight^c, Ian Allan^c, D. Liakos^d, A. S. Stasinakis^b, S. Vakalis^{a,d,*}

^a Energy Management Laboratory, Department of Environment, University of the Aegean, University Hill, Mytilene 81100, Greece

^b Water and Air Quality Laboratory, Department of Environment, University of the Aegean, University Hill, Mytilene 81100, Greece

^c Environmental Chemistry Section, Norwegian Institute for Water Research Økernveien 94, Oslo NO-0579, Norway

^d Department of Process Analysis and Plant Design, School of Chemical Engineering, National Technical School of Athens, 9 Heroon Polytechniou, Athens GR-15780, Greece

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Sludge Management
Hydrothermal Carbonization
Anaerobic Digestate
PFAS destruction
TOF-MS

ABSTRACT

Poly- and perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are frequently detected in sewage sludge and pose significant health risks due to their persistence and bioaccumulation. Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) offers a promising thermochemical method to manage sewage sludge while destroying embedded PFAS. This study investigated PFAS fate during HTC of PFAS-spiked sewage sludge under varied conditions (200–300 °C, 2 h), including tests on anaerobically digested sludge at 250 °C with different pressures and pH adjustments. Removal efficiencies for seven targeted PFAS were quantified across solid, liquid, and gas phases. The C5–C10 perfluorocarboxylates were removed by over 94 % under all experimental conditions included different temperatures (200–300 °C), pressures (38.3–68.3 bar) and pH rates (7 – 9) with NaOH and KOH, while C11 perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUnDA) and perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) showed only 55–75 % removal, indicating greater recalcitrance. Mass balance calculations confirmed extensive PFAS degradation, with less than 0.001 % transferred to the gas phase, as verified by UPLC/QTOF analysis. Notably, trace amounts of trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA) were detected in the gas phase at neutral pH but were absent at pH 9. Overall HTC performance (mass balances, pH, Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)) was evaluated, and phytotoxicity tests highlighted that the resulting hydrochar is unsuitable for use as a soil amendment.

1. Introduction

PFAS constitute persistent chemicals that have been generated by humans and extensively used since 1950 (Zhang et al., 2020). Some of their applications include consumer products, aqueous film-forming foams (AFFFs) and materials with water-resistant stuff (Zhang and Liang, 2021). Other PFAS applications contain food packaging, colour paints and cosmetic products (Gravesen et al., 2023). Their outspread use can be mainly attributed to their high stability character against degradation of heat, light, and microbial factors (Gravesen et al., 2023). Due to this, nowadays PFAS could be detected widely in the environment through the air, soil and water

* Corresponding author at: Energy Management Laboratory, Department of Environment, University of the Aegean, University Hill, Mytilene 81100, Greece.

E-mail address: svakalis@chemeng.ntua.gr (S. Vakalis).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2025.104727>

Received 19 July 2025; Received in revised form 24 December 2025; Accepted 26 December 2025

Available online 27 December 2025

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(Zhang et al., 2020). In addition, PFAS substances such as perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and PFOS have been detected in domestic and industrial wastewater at concentrations up to some hundreds ng/L (Yu et al., 2020). Their tension to accumulate to the suspended solids during wastewater treatment results to their detection to the sewage sludge produced in Sewage Treatment Plants (STPs) (Arvaniti and Stasinakis, 2015). Different classes of PFAS have been detected in sewage sludge, so far, and their concentrations range from 0.01 ng/g dw to some ug/g (Arvaniti et al., 2024). According to Zhang and Liang (2022), In a recent study, the concentrations of PFOA and PFOS ranged between 0.6–23.9 and 1.6–54.8 µg/kg in Sweden and 15–600 µg/kg PFOS in Switzerland, respectively (Zhang and Liang, 2022). Taking into account the enormous amounts of sewage sludge produced in a yearly basis, that exceed 8.9 million tones in EU-27 (Statista, 2024), and the fact that more than 50 % of the produced sludge is used in agriculture either directly or after composting, an important threat for the environment and human health exists due to the occurrence of PFAS in this matrix. The presence of PFAS in the environment for decades led to their bioaccumulation in humans, animals and plants causing bio toxic results (Li et al., 2022). Some negative effects of PFAS in human health include high cholesterol, kidney, thyroid issues, hypertension, ulcerative colitis, and testicular cancers (Gravesen et al., 2023). The management of PFAS substances has become a significant environmental challenge (Li et al., 2022) and high-temperature thermal treatments have been proposed to ensure their complete mineralization (Wu et al., 2019; Arvaniti et al., 2024).

The primary method for eliminating PFAS from different matrices and with a focus on water and sludge, is the application of thermal treatments, which apply elevated temperatures to break the chemical bonds in PFAS. Consequently, thermal technologies like incineration and pyrolysis are prominent for PFAS destruction. Incineration uses high temperatures for complete oxidation, effectively breaking down PFAS (Khan et al., 2019). Pyrolysis occurs at 300–900 ° Celsius in the absence of oxygen, producing biochar, bio-oil, and syngas, which can be used for energy recovery. Pyrolysis is advantageous as it avoids producing toxic dioxins and furans, unlike incineration, and generates useful byproducts (Serna-Sanchez, 2023). Hydrothermal liquefaction, another method, treats wet biomass at high temperatures and pressures, converting it into bio-crude oil. This process is beneficial for high-moisture biomass, avoiding the need for drying processes required in other methods like pyrolysis. HTC is an emerging, eco-friendly technology for producing carbon materials from biomass. The process converts biomass into hydrochar, a material with high heating value, without requiring prior drying. This process is energy-efficient and contributes to cleaner energy sources (Elaigwu and Greenway, 2016).

In PFAS destruction, moderating pH during hydrothermal treatment has been effective. Under alkaline conditions, PFAS degradation involves nucleophilic substitution and decarboxylation. However, the reaction varies with pH levels, with lower pH inhibiting the formation of shorter-chain perfluoroalkyl carboxylic acids (PFCAs) (Wang et al., 2019). While Hydrothermal Alkaline Treatment (HALT) effectively degrades PFAS in aqueous solutions, its impact on real-world, complex soil matrices remains under-studied (Hao et al., 2021). Regarding hydrochar production, parameters like reaction temperature and residence time significantly affect its physical-chemical properties (Altıparmakı et al., 2022). Studies show that hydrochar water extracts have lower phytotoxicity than hydrochars themselves, but the presence of potential phytotoxins like furan compounds suggests the need for further research to mitigate phytotoxicity before using hydrochars in agricultural applications (Celletti et al., 2021).

Table 1
Characteristics of the targeted PFAS.

Substance name	Acronym	Molecular Formula	Characteristics
Trifluoroacetic acid	TFA	C ₂ HF ₃ O ₂	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Released from Anthropogenic Sources Highly mobile and stable in the environment Accumulate in environmental liquors High solubility Generally low toxicity (Garavagno et al., 2024)
Perfluoropentanoic acid	PFPeA	C ₅ HF ₉ O ₂	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detected in carpets, gloves, nanosprays,leathers, ski waxes, outdoor textiles Direct exposure to the skin It enhances liver issues (Weatherly et al., 2023)
Perfluoroheptanoic acid	PFHpA	C ₇ HF ₁₃ O ₂	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Found as PFPeA in carpets, gloves, nanosprays, leather, ski wax, and outdoor textiles It has shorter life in humans but more persistent in the environment It influences negatively the liver (Weatherly et al., 2023)
Perfluorooctanoic acid	PFOA	C ₈ HF ₁₅ O ₂	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It can be found in Teflon and Gore-Tex Disposed in the environment through human applications Non-biodegradable and bioaccumulative in the environment It causes Liver toxicity (Li et al., 2017)
Perfluoro-n-nonanoic acid	PFNA	C ₉ HF ₁₇ O ₂	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is ubiquitous and persistent in the environment (Das et al., 2015) It causes oxidative stress (Rainieri et al., 2017)
Perfluorodecanoic acid	PFDA	C ₁₀ HF ₁₉ O ₂	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It can be detected in in air, food, water It can cause weight loss, loss of appetite, bradycardia, hypothermia, and thyroid issues (Li et al., 2022)
Perfluoroundecanoic acid	PFUnDA	C ₁₁ HF ₂₁ O ₂	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It can be found in soil, air and water matrices (Ivantsova et al., 2025) It causes liver toxicity (You et al., 2025)
Perfluorooctanesulfonate	PFOS	C ₈ HF ₁₇ O ₃ S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is toxic, bioaccumulative and mobile in environment (e.g. in soil, sediments, sludge and water) (Saikat et al., 2013) Exposure to it has been linked to carcinogenicity, neurotoxicity, reproductive toxicity, and immunotoxicity (Shi et al., 2024).

HTC has emerged as a promising method at the laboratory and pilot scale for treating sludge and biosolids (Wang et al., 2019). HTC transforms organic materials into a carbon-rich solid (hydrochar) under high temperature and pressure, offering benefits like carbon sequestration, energy recovery, and reduction of pathogens and odours, aligning with circular economy principles (Tasca et al., 2019). However, the knowledge on the impact of HTC on persistent and mobile substances remains limited. As regards PFAS, Zhang and Liang (2021) found that PFOA, Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA), and perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA) were completely degraded after 2 h at 250 °C, while target perfluoroalkyl sulfonic acids (PFASs) were not significantly reduced. Miserli et al. (2024) reported that the removal of PFAS from unspiked samples ranged from 55.2 % to 100 %, with the temperature and sludge-to-water ratio influencing their removal efficiency. Furthermore, there is a gap in investigating the removal of PFASs through hydrothermal carbonization under more complex experimental conditions such as different temperatures, pressures and pH, respectively, which may bring new scientific data regarding the treatment of these persistent pollutants.

A new experimental facility is being established on Lesvos Island focusing on sewage sludge treatment by integrating Anaerobic Digestion (AD) with HTC processes. The proposed system will be established at the STP in Mytilene on Lesvos Island, Greece, which is a participating stakeholder in the ZeroPM project. It is set to operate for two years, processing secondary treated sludge from various STPs across the island and biosolids from local food-processing industries. The system's configuration will consist of a sequence of processes: sludge pretreatment, advanced sludge AD, sludge dewatering, and finally HTC. Therefore, in order to assess the optimal parameters for the development of the pilot facility, several laboratory experiments will be utilized.

The aim of this study is to conduct hydrothermal experiments in order to assess the degradation of seven PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFPeA, PFHpA, perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA), perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA), PFUdA) in sewage and digested sludge through HTC, and to evaluate the potential use of the resulting hydrochars in soil conditioning. The targeted PFAS substances, selected according to a recent review study of Arvaniti et al. (2024), where these PFAS are the most common detected and studied. The focus will be on the parameters of temperature, pressure, time residence and pH. Extended characterization of the liquid and solid products of each experiment, is also performed with analysis of COD, Ammonium Nitrogen (NH₄-N), pH for the liquid samples and phytotoxicity tests, Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analysis for the solid samples. In Table 1 below the targeted PFAS are presented in more detail.

2. Materials and methods

In this study, a series of controlled hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) experiments was designed to systematically investigate PFAS removal under varying operational conditions. We conducted HTC treatments on two types of sewage sludge (raw secondary sludge and anaerobically digested sludge), each spiked with a mixture of seven target PFAS compounds. The experimental design featured variations in temperature (from 200 °C up to 300 °C), pressure (ranging approximately from 38 bar to 68 bar), and initial pH (either unadjusted at around 7 or elevated to 9 by adding NaOH/KOH), while keeping the reaction time constant at 2 h for all runs. Some trials were performed without PFAS addition as blank controls to account for background effects of the sludge matrix alone. Across all experiments, samples of the resulting solid hydrochar, liquid effluent, and gaseous outputs were collected for analysis. This approach allowed us to determine the distribution of each PFAS among the phases and calculate removal efficiencies via mass balance. In addition, the experimental plan included assessments of hydrochar properties (e.g., yield and energy content) and an ecotoxicological bioassay (seed germination test) to evaluate the broader impacts of HTC conditions. Overall, this multi-factorial design provides a comprehensive understanding of how different treatment scenarios influence PFAS fate and the quality of HTC outputs, thereby guiding optimal conditions for effective PFAS degradation in sludge.

2.1. Analytical standards and reagents

Native PFAS standards were sourced from Alfa Aesar (Germany) while mass-labelled standards of ¹³C₅-perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA), ¹³C₈-PFOA, ¹³C₉-PFNA, ¹³C₆-PFDA, ¹³C₇-PFUnDA, ¹³C₃-perfluorohexane sulfonic acid, and ¹³C₈-PFOS that were used as internal standards or surrogate standards, were supplied by Wellington Laboratories (Canada). The stock solutions of native standards were prepared in methanol (MeOH) at concentrations of 1000 mg/L, from which a mixture of target compounds was created at 160 mg/L and stored at -18 °C. LC-MS grade MeOH and acetonitrile (ACN) were purchased from Merck (Germany). Oasis Solid-Phase Extraction (SPE) HLB cartridges (200 mg, 6 mL) were supplied by Waters™ (Milford, MA, USA). Paper filters (5–13 µm) and syringe RC-filters (0.2 µm) were obtained from LIG (Germany) and Macherey-Nagel (Germany), respectively.

Table 2

HTC sludge experiments conducted in the current study. The duration of the experiments was 2 h, 100 µg/L of target compounds were added in sludge samples. The choice of this concentration was calculated based on a recent study of Arvaniti et al. (2024).

Experiment	Studied Parameters
A	Role of temperature : 200 °C, 250 °C, 300 °C
B	Role of pH : 7, 9 (using NaOH)
C	Role of P : 40 up to 66.8 bars (at 250 °C)
D	Role of KOH on PFAS destruction in gas samples
E	Results from sewage sludge and anaerobically digested sludge
F	Application of mass balances (mass yield of hydrochar)

2.2. Experimental design

Secondary sewage sludge sourced from the Mytilene STP on Lesvos Island (Greece) and anaerobically digested sludge from an upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) reactor in Antissa village of Lesvos Island, were sampled for the experimental procedures in this study. After collection, both sludges were separated from the supernatant water and were stored for the subsequent experiments. Following this separation, the sewage sludge exhibited a total solids (TS) content of 1.3 % (12.3 g/L), while the anaerobically digested sludge contained 7 % TS (61.2 g/L).

The overall experimental protocol is presented in Table 2. A total of two sets of nine experiments were carried out utilizing a 1 L capacity Parr 4577A (Moline, IL, USA) hydrothermal reactor. In the initial series, the first three experiments served as Blank-Control tests, employing sewage sludge as the raw material. These experiments were conducted under varying temperature-pressure conditions, with a pH of 7 and a residence time of 2 h. The three subsequent experiments followed the same conditions as the Blank-Control experiments but included the introduction of selected PFAS. The final three experiments emulated the conditions of the previous set, except of the pH, which was adjusted to 9 using 0.24 mg of NaOH. Two more experiments were also carried out with adjusted pH to 9 by using 0.33 mg of KOH in order to investigate the detection of PFAS substances in the gaseous phase. The pH value 7 selected to investigate the fate of PFAS with without any adjustment but the pH of the sludges as it is. Moreover, the pH value 9 chosen according to a study of Wu et al. (2019), where the removal under $\text{pH} \geq 9$ was much greater than lower rates. In addition to this, in a study of Yan et al. (2025), the results showed that the removal efficiency of PFOA under a primal pH rate around 4.6 ± 0.1 , recorded decrease from 99.4 % to 91.8 %. In all cases the role of elevated pressure on the characteristics of the products was examined. Details of the experiments are shown in Table 1, where detailed sampling has been performed from the solid and the liquid inputs/ products of hydrothermal carbonization. It should be stated that an additional aim of the experiments was to emulate the operating conditions of an pilot plant that is being developed and will operate at the Mytilene STP on Lesvos Island (Greece) in the framework of the ZeroPM project. This pilot plant will have the ability to operate up to 250 °C and therefore the experiments were kept up to this limit, with the exception of experiment A, where the study wanted to investigate the potential benefit of elevated temperatures in PFAS destruction.

Mass balances are essential tools which allow the conservation of mass within a system to be accounted for. These balances involve the meticulous tracking of mass inputs, outputs, and accumulations to gain a comprehensive understanding of how materials move and transform within a given process or system. By applying the principles of mass conservation, mass balances enable the quantification of material flows, the identification of potential losses or inefficiencies, and the optimization of processes to minimise waste and resource consumption. Mass balances provide valuable insights into the management and sustainability of processes, helping to ensure that resources are utilised efficiently, and waste generation is minimised.

As shown in Table 2, mass balance experiments were conducted during Experiment F. In total, 8 different samples were included for the flows as shown in Fig. 1. With respect to the inflows, the sludges used were separated into liquid and suspended solid samples. The products of HTC were distributed among all the phases and the gaseous part was separated further downstream from the contained tar compounds before the final measurements. Using this framework allowed the totality of inflows and outflows of the HTC process to be measured and accounted for.

After HTC experiments, the collected samples were analyzed for target PFAS. Additionally, a range of other parameters were measured to characterize the resulting products. These included COD analysis, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ and pH measurements for the liquid products, and a phytotoxicity assessment to determine the suitability of the produced hydrochars for use as soil conditioners.

Fig. 1. Representation of the sampling points during HTC of sludge used to determine mass balances (Experiment F).

2.3. Methods of analysis

2.3.1. Samples pretreatment and chromatographic analysis of PFAS

To determine the PFAS removal, liquid and solid samples were pretreated with solid-phase extraction (SPE) as described by Arvaniti et al. (2014) and submitted for LS-MS/MS analysis. In brief, all the liquid samples were filtered and adjusted to a pH of 4 ± 0.1 using acetic acid 1 N before SPE. The preparation included as first step conditioning with Oasis HLB cartridges for each sample with 6 mL of CH₃OH followed by 10 mL of H₂O ultrapure water (Milli Q). Secondly, each sample was loaded, followed by a washing step with 2×1 mL of 40 % CH₃OH in Milli-Q water, then dried for 20 min. Elution was performed with 4×1 mL of CH₃OH, followed by evaporation to dryness using N₂ gas. The final step before LC-MS analysis involved reconstitution, using 500 μ L of the mobile phase (CH₃OH/H₂O Milli Q, 50:50, v/v), with 20 μ L of the internal standard MPFOS.

Concerning the solid samples, 1 g of dried sludge was spiked with isotopically labelled internal standard ¹³C-PFAS mix (30 μ L of 0.1 ppm) and left for 30 min. Then, a mixture of 5 mL of MeOH/NH₃ (aq) (99/1) was added and extraction was performed by agitation for 30 min followed by sonication for 30 min. The supernatant was collected after centrifugation ($\times 1$) at 2700 rpm for 10 min. The extraction procedure was repeated using 3 mL of MeOH/NH₃ (aq) (99/1) this time. The two supernatants were combined and reduced in volume to 1 mL under a gentle stream of nitrogen gas (N₂). The concentrated samples were acidified with acetic acid and cleaned up using a Bond Elut Carbon cartridge (100 mg, Agilent Technologies), previously pre-conditioned with 1 mL of methanol. The cartridges were rinsed with 1 mL of methanol and the diluted samples were again concentrated to 1 mL by nitrogen gas (N₂). Finally, an aliquot of 0.2 mL of each sample was subjected to LS-MS/MS analysis after the addition of 0.1 mL of ammonium acetate solution (5.2 mM) (Bräuning et al., 2017; Higgins and Luthy, 2006).

Gas samples were collected using an active sampling approach where Evolute® ABN solid phase extraction (SPE) cartridges (Biotage, Sweden) were attached to the gas outlet. Once collected, samples were stored at -20 °C until extraction and analysis where HPLC grade methanol (Teknolab, Norway) was used. For PFAS extraction, mass-labelled standards were added to each cartridge (0.005 mL of ¹³C₃-TFA and 0.01 mL PFAS internal standard mixture) before elution with 2×5 mL methanol into a 15 mL polypropylene (PP) tube. The samples were then evaporated to 1 mL under a gentle stream of nitrogen (N₂) and transferred into a 1 mL PP vial for analysis. Instrumental analysis of gas samples was conducted using ultra performance liquid chromatography (Waters Acuity™ UPLC) coupled to a triple quadrupole time of flight (Waters Xevo® G2-S QTOF).

2.3.2. Measurements of pH and conventional pollutants in hydrochar liquid

The COD of the liquid samples was determined using the potassium dichromate method according to the Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater (APHA, 2005). The measurements occurred in a HACH DR/2400 spectrophotometer. Moreover, pH measurements of the samples performed with a De Bruyne Instruments CONSORT C932 pH meter (Wichelen, Belgium) having primarily calibrated. The Kjeldahl/trimetric method used for the assessment of NH₄-N in liquid samples according also to the Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater (APHA, 2005). All the COD measurements have been conducted in triplets.

2.3.3. Characterization of the produced hydrochar

Higher heating value (HHV) measurements performed to hydrochar samples according to the method described by Vasileiadou et al. (2022) and Altıparmakı et al. (2022). According to this method each dried hydrochar sample burned with oxygen in a bomb with the contribution of a wick inside a Parr 6400 Calorimeter (Moline, IL, USA). The temperature inside the calorimeter was 29 °C for all the measurements. In more detail, each sample weighed 0.3 g, placed in a metal capsule and a wick was placed in contact with it in order to carry out combustion with oxygen after it entered the bomb. Each measurement was carried out 2 times and each result was the average of these values.

The BET analysis plays a crucial role in material science, especially in determining the surface area of porous substances. This technique is rooted in BET theory, an advancement over the Langmuir theory, as it accounts for multilayer adsorption. This offers a deeper understanding of gas interactions with solid surfaces. The measurement of specific surface area is key in numerous applications, notably in catalysis, where it significantly impacts a material's catalytic efficiency. Additionally, BET analysis is pivotal in the pharmaceutical industry and in evaluating materials for absorption purposes, offering important insights into pore size distribution and material porosity. The surface area is measured using the BET method and nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K across a range of relative pressures, employing a 3Flex physisorption analyser (Micromeritics company, GA, USA).

2.3.4. Ammonium nitrogen in the liquid fraction (NH₄⁺-N)

Kjeldahl/trimetric method was used for the assessment of NH₄⁺-N in the liquid samples as described by ALPHA (2005). This method involved two flasks (right and left) where in the first right flask, 25 mL of buffer solution and 20 mL of the sample were added before the distillation in the Kjeldahl apparatus. The buffer solution prepared by combining 500 mL of Na₂B₄O₇:10H₂O solution (9.5 g of Na₂B₄O₇:10H₂O in 1 L of distilled water) with 88 mL of 0.1 N NaOH, and distilled water until reaching volume of 1 L. Additionally, in the left flask, 50 mL of boric acid (H₃BO₃) solution was added also before the distillation in the Kjeldahl apparatus. The boric acid solution prepared by dissolving 20 g of boric acid in distilled water and 10 mL indicator solution (mixture of 200 mg of red methyl (484) in 100 mL of ethyl alcohol and 100 mg of blue methyl (480) in 50 mL of ethyl alcohol). To complete the preparation of boric acid solution, distilled water was added to the mixture until final volume of 1 L. After the preparation of the flasks, they went through distillation in the Kjeldahl device and finally left flask underwent titration with 0.02 N H₂SO₄ for each sample. Beyond the HTC samples, one blank sample preparation also performed using distilled water as sample.

The NH₄⁺ concentrations of the liquid samples calculated with the equation below:

$$\text{CHN4} + = \left(\frac{(A - B) * 280 * f}{\text{ml of sample in the left Kjeldahl flask}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where,

A = the mL H₂SO₄ consumed by the sample

B = the mL H₂SO₄ consumed by control sample

f = Normality of H₂SO₄ solution after the titration process / Normality of the standard H₂SO₄ solution (0.02)

To define the normality of the H₂SO₄ solution, titration of H₂SO₄ solution with 0.05 N Na₂CO₃ (10 mL of 0.05 N Na₂CO₃, 90 mL of distilled water and 0.5 g of methyl orange in 100 mL of distilled water (indicator solution)) needs to be prepared. After the preparation of the solution, titration (triplicate) must be occurred on the H₂SO₄ until the change of the 0.05 N Na₂CO₃ colour. The Normality of H₂SO₄ solution can be calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{Normality of H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{solution} = \frac{(A * B)}{(53.00 * C)} \quad (2)$$

where,

A = Na₂CO₃ g/L

B = mL of 0.05 N Na₂CO₃ solution

C = mL of consumed H₂SO₄

2.4. Phytotoxicity tests

Phytotoxicity tests performed on the produced hydrochars following the method of Celletti et al. (2021). Hydrochar extracts were prepared by adding a 1/100 (w/v) ratio of hydrochar and ultrapure water for each sample. The dilution that used for the phytotoxicity tests selected after testing 4 different dilutions (1/10, 1/40, 1/80, 1/100) in hydrochar extracts obtained from the HTC experiment of digested sludge at 250 °C temperature and 40 bar and pressure rates. After dilution, all the mixtures shaken with an orbital shaker for 2 h at maximum speed and then followed centrifugation for 5 min at 4000 rpm. Before the phytotoxicity tests the extracts filtered with VWR filter papers with 10–20 µm pore size. After the filtration process, 1.2 mL of each extract added to 10 cm Petri dishes with two layers of filter paper (Whatman No. 42) in each one and 10 seeds of Cress (*Lepidium Sativum*) respectively. After the preparation of the dishes, all of them sealed with parafilm and covered with aluminium foil. All the dishes placed for incubation at 24 °C temperature rate for 48 h. All the phytotoxicity tests occurred in triplicates and after the incubation processing, all the germinated seeds in both the treated and control samples counted, and their total root lengths measured.

The germination index calculated with the followed equation:

$$GI\% = \left[\frac{(Gt \times Lt)}{(Gc \times Lc)} \right] \quad (3)$$

where, Gt is the mean number of germinated seeds, Lt is the mean of total length (cm) of the root, Gc is the mean number of germinated seeds of control test and is Lc is the mean of total length (cm) of the root of control test.

2.5. Mass balances calculations and statistical analysis

To determine the mass balances during HTC, measurements of volumes and the masses of the inputs (liquids, solids) and the outputs (liquids, solids, gases) occurred respectively. The mass balance % calculated with Eq. 4:

$$\text{Mass balance}\% = \left(\frac{M_s}{M_t} \right) \quad (4)$$

Where, M_s is the mass (ng) of the substance in the sample, and M_t is the total (t0) mass (ng) of the substance in the whole system.

The removal of PFAS in each experiment was calculated using Eq. 5:

$$\text{Removal}(\%) = \frac{M_{in} - M_{out}}{M_{in}} \quad (5)$$

Where, M_{in} and M_{out} are the masses of each studied compound at the start and at the end of the experiment, respectively.

The PFAS masses (expressed as ng) were calculated by taking into account the PFAS found both in the dissolved and solid phase according to Eq. 6:

$$M = (C_{dis} \times V) + (C_s \times TSS \times V) \quad (6)$$

where, V is the sludge volume (L), C_{dis} is the concentration of PFAS in the dissolved phase (ng/L), C_s is the concentration of PFAS on the suspended solids (ng/mg) and TS is the concentration of the total suspended solids (mg/L).

All statistical analyses were conducted with a significance level of 0.05. For comparisons involving more than two groups, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to determine if there were significant differences in mean values across the treatment

levels. This method was chosen because it effectively tests the influence of a single independent factor (e.g., temperature) on an outcome (PFAS removal) across multiple levels. In particular, one-way ANOVA was used to evaluate the effect of temperature on PFAS removal efficiencies, focusing on representative compounds (PFPeA, PFUnDA, and total PFOS). Following the approach of Liakos et al. (2025), this analysis was performed separately for the two pH regimes (neutral pH of 7 and alkaline pH of 9) in order to identify temperature effects under each constant pH condition. All statistical calculations were performed with an overall 95 % confidence level (i.e., results were considered significant at $p < 0.05$).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Mass balances of hydrothermal carbonization

Previous studies have shown that the mass yields of hydrochar produced through HTC vary widely depending on the feedstock and process conditions. Mixing low-grade coal with organic municipal solid waste in combined HTC processes can improve both the yield and quality of hydrochar (Šliz et al., 2022). This improvement is a result of chemical processes such as aromatization and dehydration, which are further influenced by the addition of substances like food waste and residues from cow dung anaerobic digestion. On the other hand, treating standard lignocellulosic biomass with HTC at higher thermal levels usually results in a reduced yield of hydrochar. This reduction is primarily due to the breakdown and hydrolysis of components like cellulose and hemicellulose in the biomass. A clear example of this is seen in lignocellulose, where the yield drops from 69.1 % to 50.1 % as the temperature increases from 215 °C to 255 °C. This decline is largely attributed to the conversion of condensable elements into gases that do not condense and to the creation of total organic carbon in the resultant liquid products. A similar pattern of reduced hydrochar yield with increased HTC temperatures is noted across various types of feedstocks (Zhi et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2018). Generally, mass yield during HTC typically ranges from 10 % to 50 % on a dry weight basis. Factors influencing mass yields include the composition of the starting material, the severity of the hydrothermal treatment (e.g., temperature, residence time, pressure), and the presence of additives or catalysts. Materials rich in organic carbon, such as sewage sludge or lignocellulosic biomass, tend to yield higher amounts of hydrochar. Achieving a balance between maximizing the production of hydrochar and minimizing process by-products is a critical consideration for optimizing HTC processes. Understanding these mass yield variations is essential for both the efficient utilization of feedstocks and the sustainable production of hydrochar, which has applications in areas ranging from bioenergy production to soil conditioning and environmental remediation. Hydrochar exhibits heating values that typically fall within the range of 15–30 MJ per kg. However, these values can vary significantly depending on several factors, including the feedstock composition, process conditions (temperature, residence time, pressure), and post-treatment procedures. The relative high heating values of hydrochar makes it a promising bioenergy resource with potential applications in various thermal processes, such as combustion, gasification, or co-firing with other fuels. Fig. 2 presents the produced hydrochar yields from HTC of sludge, along with their heating values that were found to be at the upper ranges of mass yield and heating value. The results show an increase of hydrochar yield with the elevated temperature of the HTC of the digestate while in the HTC of sludge there is a decrease at 220 °C and a following increase at 250 °C. Basso et al. (2013), highlighted the primary importance that the operation temperatures, retention times and the biomass as feedstock have in the yield of HTC products. In this case it seems that the different utilized feedstocks, according to their characteristics, influenced differently the Hydrochar formation despite the particular experimental conditions they were subjected to.

3.2. Removal of PFAS during HTC experiments

Fig. 3 illustrates the percentage (%) of total (dissolved + solid) PFAS removal for each experiment carried out at varying temperature levels during the HTC process of secondary sewage sludge. The results generally indicate high removal of PFAS under these treatment conditions, with the highest removal rates observed in experiments conducted at elevated temperatures. In more detail,

Fig. 2. Hydrochar HHV and mass yield for different HTC experiments (reaction time: 2 h).

Fig. 3. Total PFAS removal (%) in HTC experiments of secondary sewage sludge under three different temperature values (applied temperature: 200°C, 250°C, 300°C, reaction time: 2 h).

PFPeA, recorded destruction from 83.6 % to 99.4 % especially at the higher operation temperature 300 °C while the pH = 9 enhanced more the removal at lower temperatures (200 °C). Even more satisfactory removal was shown in PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, and PFDA that reached 89,7–100 % under the entire temperature and pH range except PFDA which showed a slightly higher resistance to more alkaline pH. Positive results presented also by a study of [Zhang and Liang \(2021\)](#) where their results recorded 100 % degradation of PFOA, PFHpA, PFHxA under HT of 250 °C for 2 h and 300 °C for 0.5/2 h of sludge. In addition, a bit more stability showed by the PFUdA that reached 75.3–90.5 % degradation showing vulnerability to increases in temperature and pH. [Zhang et al. \(2020\)](#) suggested that carboxylate intermediates with shorter chains, like PFPeA, exhibited lower stability when exposed to high-temperature compressed water compared to their non-fluorinated alkylcarboxylic acid counterparts, and are removed to a lesser degree. Regarding the fate of PFOA, [Yu et al. \(2020\)](#) demonstrated that at 300 °C, a defluorination rate of approximately 30 ± 6 % was achieved for PFOA. In contrast, PFOS remained largely unaffected under these conditions, with no fluoride detected in the water phase even at 350 °C. Indeed, also the results of [Fig. 3](#) reveal a higher endurance of PFOS at 200 °C and much more under pH = 9 reached removal of 45.9–73.7 %. With elevated temperature at 250 °C, the destruction increased and reached 89.0 % to 95,8 % with no important influence of pH = 9. At 300 °C the destruction reached the 99.0 % at pH = 7 while in pH = 9 noticed 98.3 % respectively. A study on sewage sludge treatment at 260 °C indicated a 35 % reduction in PFOS, but the reduction rate remained consistent despite increasing the temperature to 350 °C or prolonging the treatment duration of 30–90 min ([Yu et al., 2020](#)). This varying resistance to degradation between PFOA and PFOS suggests that the initial degradation reactions in Hydrothermal Treatment (HT) conditions likely occur at or near the compounds' polar head groups, rather than along the perfluoroalkyl chain. The research conclusively indicates that PFASs like PFOS are significantly more resistant than PFCAs under subcritical water conditions.

PFOS, widely recognized as a persistent pollutant impacting both the environment and health, breaks down thermally through recently understood processes. Studies in computational chemistry and reaction rate theory have shown that the main decomposition route for PFOS is the creation of an a-sultone, which rapidly disintegrates into perfluorooctanal and SO₂. Notably, at 1000 K, the half-life of PFOS is as short as 0.2 s, and this duration decreases with increasing temperature ([Khan et al., 2019](#)). This finding suggests that the acid component of PFOS can be efficiently dismantled in incinerators at relatively moderate temperatures, providing crucial insights for enhancing current remediation methods ([Li et al., 2022](#)).

Fig. 4. Total PFAS removal (%) in HTC experiments of anaerobically digested sludge under three different pressure values (applied temperature: 250 °C, reaction time: 2 h).

Fig. 4 illustrates the percentage (%) of target PFAS removed for each experiment conducted at varying pressures during the HTC process of anaerobically digested sludge. All experiments were conducted at 250 °C and anaerobically digested sludge was used as substrate. The results suggest that the different pressures employed during HTC processing (ranging between 38.3 and 68.2 bar) do not seem to have an impact on PFAS removal. Five out of seven PFAS were removed at a percentage higher than 94 % in all experiments, while PFUdA and PFOS (total and linear) were removed at percentages ranging between 55 % and 75 %. A slight increase of PFUdA and PFOS removal was observed when the pH increased from 7 to 9 (Fig. 4). In more detail, PFPeA, showed a slightly higher resistance in destruction from 94.0 % to 98.3 %, mainly at higher pressures while the pH had no clear effect on this. The highest removal was shown in PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, and PFDA that reached removal from 94.1 % to 100 % under all the tested conditions while it is important to be mentioned that the more alkaline pH (9) showed a clear positive effect by enhancing the destruction of PFNA, and PFDA reaching percentages of 99.2–99.6 %. In addition, PFUdA showed even more resistance than PFPeA reaching removal rates of 68.0–76.4 % but showing a slight vulnerability to the increase of pH. PFOS was the most resistant of the targeted PFAS, reaching removal rates of 59.9–77.0 % but it showed also vulnerability at the elevated pH as well as the PFPeA. In a previous study, Wu et al. (2019) explored the influence of NaOH on PFAS decomposition, reporting that NaOH, in conjunction with pH-raising agents, facilitated the breakdown and reduction of fluorine content in PFOS. Moreover, in a study of Zhang and Liang (2021) reported that by adding NaOH of 1 M, the removal of PFOS during 350 °C for 90 min residence time showed an increase. Similarly, research conducted by Hao et al. (2021) confirmed that rapid degradation and complete removal of PFOS and PFOA can be achieved within hydrothermal water through the addition of NaOH or alternative alkaline substances.

According to the above results it seems that the utilized feedstocks (secondary sewage sludge, anaerobically digested sludge) constituted an important factor in PFAS destruction due to their own different characteristics and behavior under the hydrothermal treatment. Comparing the differences between the two under hydrothermal conditions of 250 °C at 38 bar pressure, for 2 h at pH= 7 and pH= 9, the results in Fig. 5, showed that in secondary sewage sludge noted better destruction of the targeted PFAS under pH= 7 and pH= 9 than in anaerobically digested sludge. However, under pH= 9 the removal of PFNA and PFDA was better in anaerobically digested sludge that secondary sewage sludge. In addition, PFUdA and PFOS seemed also to have better removal from the secondary sewage sludge under both pH rates rather than the anaerobically digested sludge.

Further experiments at pH 7 and 9 and analysis of PFAS in different outputs of HTC of sludge (hydrochar, HTC liquid, Tar trap condensate, Tar trap gases) showed that the studied PFAS were detected at trace amounts in the gas phase. Application of mass balances showed that the part of target PFAS that passed to the gas phase was lower than 0.001 %. The presence of KOH seemed to have a positive impact in PFAS destruction in the gas phase. Specifically, and very interestingly, according to Fig. 6, trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) was detected in the experiments without pH adjustment and not at all in the experiments with pH 9. This is a significant result that highlights the effect of pH on the hydrothermal formation of TFA. A similar pattern was also observed with PFPeA, while PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, L-PFOS and Br-PFOS, had measured concentrations over 0.21 ng/cartridge for the experiments with pH 9. The alkaline pH favors the destruction of PFAS as it also showed in a study of Hao et al. (2021). In addition to this, similar results reported also from a study of Zhang and Liang (2021), where their results confirmed that the addition of Alkaline like KOH and Ca (OH)₂ enhanced the degradation of PFASs. Moreover, the decreases in concentrations noted of the tested PFAS especially showed in pH:7 according to the above results, may be due to the HALT which is a thermochemical process that occurs with subcritical water at 250 °C – 350 °C and 3.9 – 16.5 MPa pressures with alkali alternatives and is proved to achieve PFASs destruction in AFFF, AFFF-impacted wastes according to a recent study of Hao et al. (2023). The results showed 90 % degradation and defluorination of the 62 examined PFASs resulted within 90 min of HALT under 350 °C (1 M NaOH) (Hao et al., 2023). It is worth mentioning that no PFAS were detected at the Tar trap condensate

Fig. 5. Comparison of the total PFAS removal (%) in HTC experiments of secondary sewage sludge and anaerobically digested sludge (applied temperature: 250 °C, reaction time: 2 h, pH=7 and pH=9).

Fig. 6. PFAS detection in gas samples of HTC experiments of anaerobically digested sludge under different pressure values (applied temperature: 250 °C, reaction time: 2 h) and pH adjustment with KOH.

3.3. Characterization and phytotoxicity of HTC by-products

Table 3 illustrates the pH values, $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and COD concentrations of the samples after each HTC treatment. Specifically, the pH values of the anaerobically digested sludge that are treated at a constant temperature of 250 °C, but under varying pressures, seemed to be influenced by the increasing pressures applied during the treatment process. An insightful study by Zhi et al. (2024) emphasizes that the pH of the liquid phase is intricately determined by the interplay of acidic and basic functional groups. In scenarios where the reaction intensity is heightened, there is an initial decline in pH levels, followed by a subsequent increase over time (Zhi et al., 2024). This dynamic relationship between pH and the treatment conditions underscores the complexity of the hydrothermal carbonization process and its impact on the sludge's chemical properties. The full range of experiments highlighted that the trend in pH levels displayed an upward trajectory with increasing temperatures. Conversely, the decrease in pH levels observed during HTC at lower temperatures can be elucidated by the hydrolysis reactions taking place at these thermal conditions. These reactions lead to the formation of organic acids from complex organic compounds, subsequently resulting in a decline in the pH of the reaction medium. Notably, this pH shift triggers the dissolution of phosphates that are bound to calcium, as highlighted by Chen et al. This intricate interplay between temperature, hydrolysis reactions, and the dissolution of phosphate compounds underscores the multifaceted nature of the hydrothermal carbonization process and its intricate chemical transformations.

In addition, Table 3 also displays the concentrations of $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ in the liquid samples obtained from HTC experiments conducted using anaerobic digested sludge at varying pressure. A previous study by Malhotra and Garg (2023) reported that during the thermal degradation treatment of sludge, certain proteins undergo incomplete breakdown, resulting in the generation of ammonia. It is noteworthy that as the temperature of the HTC process increased, the $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentration exhibited a corresponding increase. This trend aligns with findings in a study conducted by Yan et al. (2023), where a significant portion of the nitrogen content in the liquid phase originated from $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and demonstrated a substantial rise in concentration with increasing temperature. Furthermore, research conducted by He et al. (2015) emphasized the considerable alteration in the distribution of nitrogen species within the liquid phase, primarily attributed to the elevating temperature and heightened pressure conditions employed in the process. It becomes evident that pressure variations play a substantial role in influencing $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentrations; an initial surge in $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentrations was observed as the pressure escalated from 38.3 bar to 40 bar, followed by a subsequent decline when the pressure was further elevated to 65.2 bar. This behavior aligns with similar trends observed in a study conducted by He et al. (2015), where $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentrations exhibited an increase (rising from 4020 to 6660 mg/L) when the temperature was raised from 200 °C to 260 °C and the pressure was elevated from 2 to 5 MPa. Subsequently, at higher temperatures (260 –320 °C), a decrease in $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentrations was

Table 3
pH values, $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and COD concentrations of the liquid samples of each HTC experiment.

Experimental Conditions	pH	$\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ (mg/l)	COD (mg/l)
Sewage sludge (t = 0)	7		2108.3 ± 182.8
200°C/pH= 7/ t = 2 h	5.92	154	13287.7 ± 187.6
250°C/pH= 7/ t = 2 h	6.91	350	10144.2 ± 157.0
300°C/pH= 7/ t = 2 h	7.17	602	7720.8 ± 84.0
200°C/pH= 9/ t = 2 h	6.27	280	12385.8 ± 264.9
250°C/pH= 9/ t = 2 h	7.15	560	11300.8 ± 343.3
300°C/pH= 9/ t = 2 h	7.19	672	10623.3 ± 64.8
Anaerobically digested sludge (t = 0)	7		822.7 ± 32.1
250°C/38.3 bar/pH= 7/ t = 2 h	7.04	644	12631.8 ± 109.1
250°C/40 bar/pH= 7/ t = 2 h	7.22	1064	17846.2 ± 132.5
250°C/65.2 bar/pH= 7/ t = 2 h	7.39	952	19165.7 ± 226.1
250°C/38.5 bar/pH= 9/ t = 2 h	7.38	1064	21861.1 ± 123.7
250°C/45.3 bar/pH= 9/ t = 2 h	7.64	700	13087.4 ± 77.4
250°C/67.1 bar/pH= 9/ t = 2 h	7.79	952	20279.4 ± 137.5

noted (ranging between 6400 and 3500 mg/L).

Moreover, the COD concentrations of liquid samples from HTC experiments with anaerobically digested sludge that all conducted at a consistent temperature of 250 °C but at varying pressures, agreed with the findings of a study of Vasileiadou et al. (2022), reported that an increase in pressure corresponded to an increase in COD concentrations. However, it is noteworthy that in the subsequent measurements a distinct pattern emerges. Initially, there is a decrease in concentrations in the experiment conducted at 250 bar, followed by another increase at 300 bar. These results are in line with the outcomes reported in a study by Hao et al. (2021), where it was observed that the addition of NaOH led to an increase in COD concentrations during the hydrothermal treatment. This variation in COD concentrations under different conditions underscores the complexity of the hydrothermal carbonization process and its sensitivity to factors like pressure and pH adjustment. Comparison of the experiments conducted under identical conditions of temperature (250 °C) and pressure (38 bar) in the two distinct sludge types, highlights a notable disparity in the COD concentrations observed. Specifically, the COD concentrations of the anaerobically digested sludge subjected to hydrothermal treatment were significantly higher than those of the sewage sludge following the same treatment conditions. This disparity suggests inherent differences in the organic composition or reactivity of the two sludge types under these conditions. Furthermore, it is worth considering that the adjustment of pH to 9 using NaOH may have played a contributing role in the observed increase in COD concentrations. This adjustment likely introduced variations in the chemical environment, potentially impacting the hydrothermal reactions and organic compound breakdown, thus influencing the COD concentrations in the final products.

Finally, the COD concentrations of the liquid samples from HTC experiments with secondary sewage sludge at 200 °C, 250 °C and 300 °C temperature rates showed a rapid increase after hydrothermal treatment of the raw sludge. Similar results were noticed in a previous study from Altiparmaki et al. (2022), where the results revealed that at lower temperature operating conditions of HTC, the first process that takes place is hydrolysis, leading to subsequent production of carbon dioxide and implying the transition of carbon into the gaseous phase. Moreover, another important factor that contributes to the interpretation of the results is the capture of carbon during the formation of hydrochar which justifies the initial increase of COD concentrations and followed by a subsequent decrease (Altiparmaki et al., 2022).

The phytotoxicity experiments were based on the method that was introduced by Celletti et al. (2021) and assessed the germination index of the hydrochar extracts from variously treated anaerobic and sewage sludge. The results are presented in Fig. 7 and show the increased germination index with increased pressure of treatment. The results show that the hydrochar is not an ideal substrate for plant growth and this result can be expected from the increased production of organic acids during hydrothermal carbonization. It is suggested that more experiments have to be performed on other hydrochars, because the existing literature indicates that hydrochar is a suitable soil amendment and in this study we contradict this point.

The BET analysis results are presented in Fig. 8, where the surface area and the total pore size of different hydrochars are being presented. There is a clear correlation between the surface area and the total pore size with the pressure of the process and this is an interesting parameter that needs to be considered for applications of hydrochar as an absorbent. Nonetheless, the characteristics of the material are significantly inferior to biochar as it is produced in several studies (Ahmad et al., 2021). Overall, in the manuscript, it should be highlighted that the BET, LC-MS/MS, and TOF-MS analyses, we note that these methods were conducted under strictly controlled conditions using autosamplers and validated protocols. As such, replicate runs yielded identical values within the detection limits of the instruments, and variability was negligible.

Fig. 9 illustrates the mass balance results from HTC experiments at 250 °C under varying pressures and pH conditions, revealing notable differences in the fate of various PFAS. Most targeted PFAS compounds, including PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, and PFUnDA, underwent significant degradation, with their mass largely disappearing from both the hydrochar and liquid and gas fractions. However, PFOS exhibited distinct resilience, predominantly remaining in the hydrochar with only minor amounts detected in the liquid phase. In Table 4 below, the results of the % Degradation of the targeted substances in all fractions (liquid, solid, gas) are presented in more detail. Analyzing the results, PFPeA removed completely under 250 °C and alkaline pH (pH = 9) while it recorded a little remaining in the gas phase of the order of 0,000340 % under neutral pH (pH = 7). Interesting is also the fate of PFHpA, PFOA,

Fig. 7. Phytotoxicity test of hydrochar for various pressures of hydrothermal carbonization.

Fig. 8. Surface are and total pore size (BET analysis) of hydrochars produced via hydrothermal carbonization in various temperatures and pressures.

Fig. 9. Mass balances of HTC experiments of anaerobically digested sludge under 38.6 bar (up left), 66.8 bar pressure (up right), 38.5 bar/pH:9 (down left) and 52.5 bar/pH:9 (down right). In all cases the temperature of treatment was 250 °C and the reaction time 2 h.

PFNA, PFDA where these substances completely removed from both the liquid and the solid phase in all the tested experimental conditions that are presented in this table, but one order of 0,000024 % to 0,000587 % of these substances remained in the gas phase. PFUnDA seemed to be completely removed under neutral pH (pH = 7) and 38.6 bar pressure while some residues remained also in the gas phase under higher pressure and pH rates.

Table 4

% Degradation of the targeted substances in all mass fractions (liquid, solid, gas).

% Degradation	PFPeA	PFHpA	PFOA	PFNA	PFDA	PFUnDA	L-PFOS
250 °C/38.6 bar	99.999660	99.999856	99.999831	99.999885	99.999976	100.000000	1.433031
250 °C/66.8 bar	100.000000	99.999909	99.999859	99.999806	99.999695	99.999413	26.515081
250 °C/38.5 bar/pH= 9	100.000000	99.999970	99.999941	99.999973	99.999973	99.999947	1.147946
250 °C/52.5 bar/pH= 9	100.000000	99.999961	99.999924	99.999944	99.999879	99.999708	27.540393

This contrasting behavior can be attributed to the unique chemical structure of PFOS, which features a sulfonate group that imparts enhanced thermal stability and resistance to defluorination compared to the carboxylate groups present in other PFAS. In more detail, the highest removal of PFOS recorded under higher operated pressures and alkaline pH (pH = 9). Most of the PFOS remained in the solid phase (hydrochar) with the highest 90,906167 % noted in 250°C/38.5 bar/pH:9 and the lowest 61,871194 % in 250°C/52.5 bar/pH:9. The hydrophobic character of its fluorinated tail likely promotes strong adsorption onto the carbon-rich matrix of the hydrochar, further inhibiting its degradation. Although some experiments incorporated an alkaline pH (adjusted to 9), which is known to facilitate PFAS breakdown through nucleophilic substitution mechanisms, this modification did not substantially alter the distribution of PFOS. As for the other fractions (liquid, gas), the highest percentage of PFOS remaining was 10,588376 % in 250°C/52.5 bar/pH:9 and the lowest recorded 4,809446 % in 250°C/38.6 bar while in the gas phase no PFOS remained in 250°C/38.6 bar and the highest measured 0,000038 % in 250°C/52.5 bar/pH:9 respectively. The persistence of PFOS under the tested subcritical conditions underscores the challenges associated with its complete removal and suggests that more severe thermochemical treatments, such as those involving supercritical water, may be required to achieve effective degradation.

These findings are critical when considering the environmental application of hydrochar, particularly as a soil amendment, since residual PFOS could pose significant ecological and health risks. Future research should focus on optimizing HTC parameters—including temperature, pressure, and pH—to enhance the breakdown of recalcitrant substances like PFOS and ensure safer end-use of the by-products. One-way ANOVA confirmed that temperature had a statistically significant effect on the removal efficiencies of PFPeA, PFUDA, and total PFOs at both pH 9 and pH 7. Under alkaline conditions (pH 9), the analysis yielded an F-statistic of 4635.72 with an associated p-value of 3.27×10^{-28} , far exceeding the critical F value (approximately 2.51 at the 5 % significance level). This extremely large F-statistic and negligible p-value indicate that the null hypothesis (no temperature influence) can be decisively rejected, meaning that variations in temperature at pH 9 led to significant changes in the removal of these PFAS compounds. Likewise, at neutral pH 7, the temperature effect was highly significant ($F = 259.28$, $p = 5.55 \times 10^{-17}$), with the F-statistic greatly surpassing the critical threshold and the p-value indicating a pronounced impact of temperature on PFPeA, PFUDA, and total PFOs removal. Thus, in both pH regimes, temperature is confirmed as a significant factor influencing PFAS removal efficiency during hydrothermal carbonization.

4. Conclusions

The HTC process proved highly effective in degrading PFAS in sewage and digested sludge while generating an energy-rich hydrochar. Specifically, PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, and PFDA were removed at rates exceeding 94 % across experiments conducted at 200 °C, 250 °C, and 300 °C for 2 h. In contrast, PFUDA and PFOS showed lower removal efficiencies, with percentages ranging between 55 % and 75 %. The study also indicated that adjusting the pH to 9 using NaOH or KOH significantly enhanced PFAS destruction, while varying the pressure -from approximately 38–66 bar- had a minimal impact on removal rates. Notably, mass balance assessments confirmed that less than 0.001 % of the initial PFAS mass transferred to the gaseous phase during HTC. In addition to PFAS degradation, the process yielded a hydrochar with heating values in the upper range of 15–30 MJ/kg, and mass yields typical of HTC processes (generally between 10 % and 50 % on a dry weight basis). However, phytotoxicity tests indicated that the produced hydrochar, likely due to the generation of organic acids during treatment, is unsuitable for use as a soil amendment. The numerical outcomes, including the high PFAS removal rates and the minimal gaseous emissions, underscore HTC's potential as a robust treatment technology for persistent contaminants. The ANOVA results underscore the pH-dependent nature of temperature effects on removal performance. While temperature significantly influenced removal at pH 7, no such effect was observed at pH 9. The resistance of PFOS and PFUDA under the tested subcritical conditions indicates that further investigation into more intense treatments, i.e. hydrothermal liquefaction or gasification, should be the next step in order to achieve full removal. (Table 5 and 6)

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Liakos Dimitrios: Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ian Allan:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Emma Knight:** Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Gatidou Georgia:** Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Altiparmaki Georgia:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation. **Vakalis Stergios:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Stasinakis Athanasios:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Table 5

One-way ANOVA for the influence of temperature on the reduction of PFPeA, PFUDA, and total PFOs and for pH:9.

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	F crit
The factor of temperature at pH 9						
Between the groups	66663729.32	8	8332966.165	4635.7237	3.26996E-28	2.510157895
Inside the groups	32355.98165	18	1797.554536			
Total	66696085.3	26				

Table 6

One-way ANOVA for the influence of temperature on the reduction of PFPeA, PFUDA, and total PFOs and for pH:7.

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	F crit
The factor of temperature at pH 7						
Between the groups	14417045	8	1802130.634	259.2776	5.54985E-17	2.510157895
Inside the groups	125110.5	18	6950.583911			
Total	14542156	26				

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT 5 in order to improve language and readability, with caution. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This project received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101036756, ZeroPM.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.eti.2025.104727](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2025.104727).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Ahmad, J., Vakalis, S., Patuzzi, F., Baratieri, M., 2021. Effect of process conditions on the surface properties of biomass chars produced by means of pyrolysis and CO₂ gasification (Available at:). *Energy Environ.* 32 (8), 1378–1396. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0958305X20948237>.
- Altiparmaki, G., Vasileiadou, M.A., Vakalis, S., 2022. The effect of excess water on the hydrothermal carbonization of anise waste from ouzo production on Lesbos island. *Sustain. Chem. Pharm.* 29 (2022), 100831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scp.2022.100831>.
- APHA, 2005. *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater*, 21st ed. American Public Health Association, USA.
- Arvaniti, O.S., Asimakopoulos, A.G., Dasenaki, M.E., Ventouri, E.I., Stasinakis, A.S., Thomaidis, N.S., 2014. Simultaneous determination of eighteen perfluorinated compounds in dissolved and particulate phases of wastewater, and in sewage sludge by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *Anal. Methods* 6, 1341–1349. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3AY42015A>.
- Arvaniti, O.S., Fountoulakis, M.S., Gatidou, G., Kalantzi, O.I., Vakalis, S., Stasinakis, A.S., 2024. Perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances in sewage sludge: challenges of biological and thermal treatment processes and potential threats to the environment from land disposal. *Environ. Sci. Eur.* 36, 207. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-024-01031-3>.
- Arvaniti, O.S., Stasinakis, A.S., 2015. Review on the occurrence, fate and removal of perfluorinated compounds during wastewater treatment. *Sci. Total Environ.* 524–525, 81–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.04.023>.
- Basso, D., Castello, D., Baratieri, M., & Fiori, L. (2013, June). Hydrothermal carbonization of waste biomass: Progress report and prospects. In *Proceedings of the 21th European Biomass Conference and Exhibition, Copenhagen* (pp. 3-7).
- Bräunig, J., Baduel, C., Heffernan, A., Rotander, A., Donaldson, E., Mueller, J.F., 2017. Fate and redistribution of perfluoroalkyl acids through AFFF-impacted groundwater. *Sci. Total Environ.* 596, 360–368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.04.095>.
- Celletti, S., Bergamo, A., Benedetti, V., Pecchi, M., Patuzzi, F., Basso, B., Baratieri, M., Cesco, S., Tanja Mimmo, T., 2021. Phytotoxicity of hydrochars obtained by hydrothermal carbonization of manure-based digestate. *J. Environ. Manag.* 280, 111635. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.111635>.

- Das, K.P., Grey, B.E., Rosen, M.B., Wood, C.R., Tatum-Gibbs, K.R., Zehr, R.D., Strynar, M.J., Lindstrom, A.B., Lau, C., 2015. Developmental toxicity of perfluorononanoic acid in mice. *Reprod. Toxicol.* 51, 133–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reprotox.2014.12.012>.
- Elaigwu, S.E., Greenway, G.M., 2016. Microwave-assisted and conventional hydrothermal carbonization of lignocellulosic waste material: comparison of the chemical and structural properties of the hydrochars. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* 118, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2015.12.013>.
- Garavagno, M.D.L.A., Holland, R., Khan, M.A.H., Orr-Ewing, A.J., Shallcross, D.E., 2024. Trifluoroacetic acid: toxicity, sources, sinks and future prospects. *Sustainability* 16 (6), 2382. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16062382>.
- Gravesen, C.R., Lee, L.S., Choi, Y.J., Silveira, M.L., Judy, J.D., 2023. PFAS release from wastewater residuals as a function of composition and production practices. *Environ. Pollut.* 322, 121167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2023.121167>.
- Hao, S., Choi, Y.-J., Wu, B., Higgins, C.P., Deeb, R., Strathmann, T.J., 2021. Hydrothermal alkaline treatment for destruction of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in aqueous film-forming foam. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 55 (5), 3283–3295. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c06906>.
- Hao, S., Reardon, P.N., Choi, Y.J., Zhang, C., Sanchez, J.M., Higgins, C.P., Strathmann, T.J., 2023. Hydrothermal alkaline treatment (HALT) of foam fractionation concentrate derived from PFAS-contaminated groundwater. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 57 (44), 17154–17165. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.3c05140>.
- Higgins, C.P., Luthy, R.G., 2006. Sorption of perfluorinated surfactants on sediments. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 40, 7251–7256. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es061000n>.
- Ivantsova, E., Sultan, A., Martyniuk, C.J., 2025. Occurrence and toxicity mechanisms of perfluorononanoic acid, perfluorodecanoic acid, and perfluoroundecanoic acid in fish: a review. *Toxics* 13 (6), 436. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics13060436>.
- Khan, M.Y., So, S., Silva, G., 2019. d. Decompos. Kinet. perfluorinated sulfonic Acids. <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv.8306414.v1>.
- Li, K., Gao, P., Xiang, P., Zhang, X., Cui, X., Ma, L.Q., 2017. Molecular mechanisms of PFOA-induced toxicity in animals and humans: implications for health risks. *Environ. Int.* 99, 43–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2016.11.014>.
- Li, K., Zhao, Q., Fan, Z., Jia, S., Liu, Q., Liu, F., Liu, S., 2022. The toxicity of perfluorodecanoic acid is mainly manifested as a deflected immune function. *Mol. Biol. Rep.* 49 (6), 4365–4376. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11033-022-07272-w>.
- Liakos, D., Altıparmakı, G., Malamis, S., Vakalis, S., 2025. Hydrothermal liquefaction for biofuel synthesis: assessment of VFA (Volatile Fatty Acid) and FAME (Fatty Acid Methyl Ester) profiles from spent coffee grounds. *Energies* 18 (8), 2094. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en18082094>.
- Malhotra, M., Garg, A., 2023. Hydrothermal carbonization of sewage sludge: Optimization of operating conditions using design of experiment approach and evaluation of resource recovery potential. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11 (2), 109507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.109507>.
- Miserli, K., Boti, V., Konstantinou, I., 2024. Analysis of perfluorinated compounds in sewage sludge and hydrochar by UHPLC LTQ/Orbitrap MS and removal assessment during hydrothermal carbonization treatment. *Sci. Total Environ.* 929, 172650. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172650>.
- Rainieri, S., Conlledo, N., Langerholc, T., Madorran, E., Sala, M., Barranco, A., 2017. Toxic effects of perfluorinated compounds at human cellular level and on a model vertebrate. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 104, 14–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2017.02.041>.
- Saikat, S., Kreis, I., Davies, B., Bridgman, S., Kamanyire, R., 2013. The impact of PFOS on health in the general population: a review. *Environ. Sci. Processes Impacts* 15 (2), 329–335. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C2EM30698K>.
- Shi, W., Zhang, Z., Li, M., Dong, H., Li, J., 2024. Reproductive toxicity of PFOA, PFOS and their substitutes: a review based on epidemiological and toxicological evidence. *Environ. Res.* 250, 118485. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2024.118485>.
- Śliz, M., Czerwińska, K., Magdziarz, A., Lombardi, L., Wilk, M., 2022. Hydrothermal carbonization of the wet fraction from mixed municipal solid waste: a fuel and structural analysis of hydrochars. *Energies* 15 (18), 6708. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15186708>.
- Statista (2024) Sewage sludge produced and disposed in Europe in 2020, by country (<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1393771/sewage-sludge-generation-europe/>, last access: 15.01.2025).
- Tasca, A.L., Puccini, M., Gori, R., Corsi, I., Galletti, A.M.R., Vitolo, S., 2019. Hydrothermal carbonization of sewage sludge: a critical analysis of process severity, hydrochar properties and environmental implications. *Waste Manag.* 93, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.05.027>.
- Vasileiadou, M.A., Altıparmakı, G., Moustakas, K., Vakalis, S., 2022. Quality of hydrochar from wine sludge under variable conditions of hydrothermal carbonization: the case of Lesbos Island. *Energies* 15 (10), 3574. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15103574>.
- Wang, L., Chang, Y., Li, A., 2019. Hydrothermal carbonization for energy-efficient processing of sewage sludge: a review. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 108, 423–440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.04.011>.
- Wang, T., Zhai, Y., Zhu, Y., Li, C., Zeng, G., 2018. A review of the hydrothermal carbonization of biomass waste for hydrochar formation: process conditions, fundamentals, and physicochemical properties. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 90, 223–247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.03.071>.
- Weatherly, L.M., Shane, H.L., Lukomska, E., Baur, R., Anderson, S.E., 2023. Systemic toxicity induced by topical application of perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA), perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA), and perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA) in a murine model. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 171, 113515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2022.113515>.
- Wu, B., Hao, S., Choi, Y., Higgins, C.P., Deeb, R., Strathmann, T.J., 2019. Rapid destruction and defluorination of perfluorooctanesulfonate by alkaline hydrothermal reaction. *Environ. Sci. Technol. Lett.* 6 (10), 630–636. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.estlett.9b00506>.
- Yan, M., Chen, F., Li, T., Zhong, L., Feng, H., Xu, Z., Hantoko, D., Wibowo, H., 2023. Hydrothermal carbonization of food waste digestate solids: Effect of temperature and time on products characteristic and environmental evaluation. *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* 178, 296–308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2023.08.010>.
- Yan, Z., Sun, Y., Yan, J., Liu, R., Zhang, J., Song, J., 2025. Rapid adsorption of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) on N-doped porous carbons (NPCs) derived from ZIF-8 over a wide pH range: adsorption behaviors and mechanisms. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 365, 132575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2025.132575>.
- You, L., Wang, X., Zhi, Y., Wang, H., Zhuang, Z., Yang, J., Zhang, Q., Shang, H., Li, Y., Wan, Y., Jia, X., Yang, H., 2025. Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances suppress macrophage alternative activation to disrupt hepatic lipid metabolism. *Chem. Res. Toxicol.* <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrestox.5c00066>.
- Yu, J., Nickerson, A., Li, Y., Fang, Y., Strathmann, T.J., 2020. Fate of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) during hydrothermal liquefaction of municipal wastewater treatment sludge. *Environ. Sci. Water Res. Technol.* 6 (5), 1388–1399. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9EW01139K>.
- Zhang, W., Cao, H., Mahadevan Subramanya, S., Savage, P., Liang, Y., 2020. Destruction of perfluoroalkyl acids accumulated in *Typha latifolia* through hydrothermal liquefaction. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 8 (25), 9257–9262. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.0c03249>.
- Zhang, W., Liang, Y., 2021. Effects of hydrothermal treatments on destruction of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in sewage sludge. *Environ. Pollut.* 285, 117276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.117276>.
- Zhang, W., Liang, Y., 2022. Hydrothermal liquefaction of sewage sludge—effect of four reagents on relevant parameters related to bioclude and PFAS. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 10 (1), 107092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.107092>.
- Zhi, Y., Xu, D., Jiang, G., Yang, W., Chen, Z., Duan, P., Zhang, J., 2024. A review of hydrothermal carbonization of municipal sludge: process conditions, physicochemical properties, methods coupling, energy balances and life cycle analyses. *Fuel Process. Technol.* 254, 107943. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2023.107943>.